

TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND MODERN STRATEGIES IN MUSIC TEACHING

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Abstract.

This article discusses technological processes and modern pedagogical strategies in music education.

Keywords: innovation, process, innovation, system, blocks, methods, approaches.

The idea of technology of education is not new. Czech pedagogue 400 years ago Yan Amos Comenius put forward the idea of technologyization of education. He encouraged education to be "technical", that is, everything should be taught to be successful. He called the educational process leading to the result "didactic machine". Specific goals for such a didactic machine; to achieve these goals, clearly adapted means; wrote that it is important to find clear rules for how to use these tools. In the theory and practice of education, the first attempts were made in the 1950s to give the educational process a technological character. They express themselves in the creation of complex technical tools designed for traditional teaching.

Currently, "music teaching technology and design" is not considered as research in the field of teaching techniques or computer use, but through the analysis of factors that increase educational efficiency, the creation and application of methods and materials, as well as having a specific goal of determining the principles of the educational process and developing the most optimal ways by evaluating the methods used. Innovation (English innovation) is innovation. A. I. Prigozhin understands the purposeful changes that introduce new, relatively stable elements to a certain social unit - organization, population, society, group. This is the activity of the innovator.

The main components of the technological process

New pedagogical technology, ped-technological knowledge	The conclusion of scientific research, inventiveness, conclusions and proposals of methodical associations of experimental areas, results of science and scientific achievements, understanding, methodical recommendations
Introducing innovation with the advent of technology	Methodological and theoretical foundations of the application of pedagogical technologies in accordance with the requirements of the quality world educational standard improved by the result of the application of new knowledge and its application.

Diffusion technology	Adopted as a novelty and once widespread, but known social conditions, technological processes.
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Researchers (A.I. Prigozhin, B.V. Sazonov, V.S. Tolstoy, A.G. Kruglikov, A.S. Akhiezer, N.P. Stepanov, etc.) distinguish two approaches to studying the components of innovation processes: the individual microlevel of innovation and the microlevel of the interaction of individually introduced innovations.

In the first approach, some new idea introduced into life is highlighted.

In the second approach, the interaction of separately introduced innovations, their unity, competition and, as a result, the replacement of one by another.

When analyzing the microstructure of the innovation process, scientists distinguish the concept of periodicity of life. This concept stems from the fact that innovation is a measurable process. In the literature on pedagogy, a scheme of the innovation process is given. It covers the following steps:

- ❖ *The stage of the birth of a new idea or the emergence of a new concept, it is also called the stage of discovery.*
- ❖ *Invention, i.e. the stage of innovation.*
- ❖ *The stage of being able to apply the created innovation in practice.*
- ❖ *The stage of spreading the news, its wide application.*
- ❖ *The stage of dominance of innovation in a particular field. At this stage, the novelty loses its novelty, its effective alternative appears.*
- ❖ *The stage of reducing the scope of application of the innovation by replacing it based on a new alternative.*

V.A. Slastenin considers innovation to be a set of purpose-oriented innovation creation, wide distribution and use process, its purpose is to satisfy people's needs and aspirations with new tools. The authors of the systematic concept of innovation (A.I. Prigozhin, B.V. Sazonov, V.S. Tolstoy) distinguish two important forms of innovation processes.

A simple development of innovation is included in the first form. This applies to organizations that have adopted the product for the first time.

The second form refers to the large-scale development of the innovation.

Innovation is both an internal logic and a dynamic system that develops legally over time and expresses its interaction with the environment. The concept of "new" occupies a central place in pedagogical innovation. It also arouses interest in special, conditional, local and subjective innovation in pedagogical science.

According to V.A. Slastenin, the private innovation, the current modernization envisages updating one of the elements of a specific system product. Conditional innovation is a combination of certain elements that lead to complex and progressive innovation.

Local novelty is determined by the use of novelty in a concrete object.

Subjective novelty is determined by the fact that the object itself is new for a given object.

The concepts of novelty and innovation are different in scientific fields. Innovation is a tool: a new method, methodology, technology, etc. V.I. Zagvyazinsky defined the new concept and said that the new in pedagogy is not just an idea, but approaches, methods, technologies that have not yet been used, but the elements of the pedagogical process are combined or taken separately, and education in changing conditions and situations and reflects the beginnings of effectively solving educational tasks. R. N. Yusufbekova considers pedagogical innovation as a previously unknown and previously unrecorded situation, result, evolving theory and content of pedagogical reality leading to practice. In pedagogical innovation, R. N. Yusufbekova distinguishes three blocks of the structure of the innovation process:

The first block is a new separation block in pedagogy. This includes the classification of new, pedagogical innovation in pedagogy, conditions for creating something new, norms of innovation, readiness for mastering and using the new, tradition and innovation, stages of creating something new in pedagogy.

The second block is the block of perception, assimilation and evaluation of the new: pedagogical communities, diversity of processes of evaluation and assimilation of the new, conservatism and innovation in pedagogy, innovation environment, readiness of pedagogical communities to perceive and evaluate the new.

The third block is the block of new use and its implementation, that is, the laws and types of new implementation, use and wide implementation. M.M. Potashnik's interpretations of innovation processes attract people's attention. It gives the following structure of the innovation process:

➤ *the structure of activity - motive - goal - task - content - form - methods - sum of methodology components;*

➤ *international, regional, district, city and other levels of subjective structure-innovative activity subjects;*

➤ *level structure-international, regional, district, city and other levels of innovative activity subjects;*

➤ *content structure - emergence, development and assimilation of innovation in educational and educational work, management (etc.);*

➤ *periodic structure of life based on stages - emergence of novelty - rapid growth - maturity - assimilation - diffusion (absorption, spread) - enrichment (saturation) - backwardness - crisis - irradiation (deception) - age spiritualization;*

➤ *management structure - interaction of 4 types of management actions: planning - organizing - leading - controlling;*

organizational structure - diagnostic, predictive, purely organizational, practical, generalizing, implementing.

So, technology and design in music lessons is an educational method, in a certain sense, an educational process, a set of tools, forms and methods. Selection of educational materials, processing, changing the shape and size of the subject according to the specific structure of the subject, the ability of the students, and the level of mastery of the subject are related to the educational technology. The teacher's organization of the educational process based on

technological methods largely depends on him, his knowledge and familiarity with the organizational structure of each of them is an important guarantee of educational effectiveness. Therefore, innovative technology consists of the activity of influencing a person according to a predetermined goal.

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